

Imago
Data Service
for Imagery

The State of Imagery 2024–25

About us

Part of Smart Data Research UK, Imago is the Imagery Data Service for sustainability, prosperity and wellbeing. We translate complex satellite imagery into research-ready data products, specifically tailored for social researchers, policymakers and practitioners.

We bring together expertise from across the UK and USA, including the University of Liverpool, Newcastle University, Harvard University and University of Manchester. Our team is built of researchers, research software engineers and professional services across disciplines and career stages.

Satellites capture detailed and comprehensive data of the Earth. From urban development to green spaces to pollution, this imagery can help us address the UK's most complex challenges in wellbeing, prosperity and sustainability. However, extracting actionable insights from raw imagery can be overwhelming and out-of-reach for non-specialists.

At Imago, our mission is to make satellite imagery more **useful**, **usable** and **used** across social research and policy. We work with academics, data providers, practitioners and policymakers to create data products that unlock new insights and meet users where they are. This includes research-ready products, intuitive interfaces and capacity building.

Our work is built on three core pillars:

Imagery innovation:

We co-produce research-ready data products by building partnerships with data providers, developing advanced computational methods and establishing robust technical infrastructure.

Our service uses both established earth observation techniques and AI to extract value from imagery and combines it with our social science expertise to produce flexible indicators for custom geographies and time periods — whether tracking urban development or changes in urban greenspace.

Data for all:

A key goal is ensuring that satellite-derived data is accessible to a diverse range of users. We are working towards delivering a platform that provides a user-friendly interface, interactive mapping and advanced search tools.

Data products are delivered in widely used formats, with clear metadata and documentation, and are linked to existing surveys and cohort studies. Strategic partnerships with other data services and an advisory board help to avoid duplication and maximise collaboration across the UK's data landscape.

Capability and community:

We want to create and nurture a community around imagery. To achieve this, we build capacity for working with imagery across disciplines and career stages by delivering training materials, bootcamps, an open textbook and a yearly report on the state of imagery.

We also host community events such as our annual summit. Collaborative research projects demonstrate the unique value of imagery for urgent policy areas.

Foreword — liftoff!

Welcome to our first Imago State of Imagery. It's been a big orbit around the sun for us — our first full project year.

The **State of Imagery** is an annual reflection on what Imago has achieved and where we are headed. We intend this document to be both a report and a conversation starter: it shares updates on our progress, highlights emerging opportunities and challenges, and looks ahead to scope how imagery can illuminate the social, economic, health and environmental dynamics shaping our world.

When 2025 began, Imago was a small, ambitious group of academics — full of ideas but short on muscle. Since then, we've built a diverse and interdisciplinary team we're extremely proud of.

Today, Imago is a growing collective spanning four universities, made up of researchers, research software engineers and professional services across disciplines and career stages, which develops data products, builds robust infrastructure, and expands our partnerships and outreach. This is what it takes to make satellite imagery more useful, usable and used across social research and policy.

We believe imagery is not just a tool for observation, but a vital resource for understanding and addressing the complex social realities unfolding on the ground. As the relevance of satellite data continues to grow, especially for social and policy research, Imago's role is to bridge the gap between technical possibility and practical insight.

Dani Arribas-Bel
University of Liverpool, Director

Rachel Franklin
Harvard University, Co-Director

This year has been about building foundations, from the launch of our website and data catalogue to the first releases of data products designed to make satellite imagery more accessible to researchers and policymakers alike.

This is only the tip of the iceberg, however. Behind the scenes, there is a great deal of computing infrastructure, pipelines and code that has started taking shape to make these products (and those to come!) possible in efficient, reproducible and transparent ways. Perhaps most important of all, we have made great strides in building human infrastructure: the connective tissue that brings people and teams from disparate origins together with a shared purpose.

We release this first edition of the **State of Imagery** at Imago's first Annual Summit. If the State is our chance to sum up what we are up to, the Summit is our opportunity to bring it to you in person. We see the event as a mark on the calendar to share our journey, celebrate our community and collectively reflect on how imagery can inform better decisions, research, and policy.

We hope this is the beginning of a fruitful conversation — one that continues to make imagery more meaningful and impactful for all who seek to understand and improve the social world around us.

Elisabetta Pietrostefani
University of Liverpool, Co-Director

Paul Watson
Newcastle University, Co-Director

The experts behind Imago's vision

Behind Imago are our two advisory boards: our technical advisory board and our community advisory board.

Our technical board advises on strategy and critical choices on architecture and deployment of the underpinning computational platform, and our community board on opportunities and issues around potential partnerships and data product design, integration and delivery.

These boards bring together an international array of world-class leaders across industry, government and academia.

Technical advisory board

Budhu Bhaduri

Director of Science, Programs and Partnerships, National Security Sciences, Oak Ridge National Labs (ORNL)

Alex de Sherbinin

Director, Center for International Earth Science Information Network, Columbia University

Rachel Gaulton

Remote Sensing and GIS Lead, Fera Science Ltd

Joseph Mascaro

Director of Science Program, Planet

John Remedios

Director, National Centre for Earth Observation

Shaowen Wang

Digital and Spatial Studies, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

Community advisory board

Doreen Boyd

Professor of Earth Observation, University of Nottingham

Lewis Dijkstra

Head of Urban and Territorial Analysis, European Commission Joint Research Centre

Monika Kuffer

Professor on Sustainability of Rural-Urban Systems, University of Twente

Darla Munroe

Director of Research, Lincoln Institute of Land Policy

Beth Tellman

Assistant Professor, University of Wisconsin-Madison

I am a globally recognized expert in geospatial science and data-driven modelling. With over 25 years at ORNL, I lead pioneering research integrating remote sensing, artificial intelligence and high-performance computing to extract actionable insights from satellite and aerial imagery. My work has advanced applications in population mapping, urban dynamics, environmental monitoring and human security. As Founding Director of ORNL's Urban Dynamics Institute and leader of U.S. Department of Energy's Geospatial Sciences initiatives, I have developed innovative methods and partnerships that transform complex imagery data into strategic decision-support capabilities.

Budhendra (Budhu) Bhaduri — Technical Advisory Board

Remote sensing has been a critical ingredient in policy responses to environmental problems from the ozone hole, deforestation, biodiversity loss and climate change. Without its contribution, we would literally be flying blind when it comes to global environmental governance.

Alex de Sherbinin — Technical Advisory Board

My research sits at the intersection of remote sensing, geography and human rights, using satellite imagery to expose and quantify issues such as modern slavery, deforestation and environmental change. My vantage point uniquely combines spatial data science with social justice, transforming pixels into insights about human vulnerability and planetary health. My use of imagery transcends traditional cartography and uses a range of resolutions and technologies. This is required as I interpret landscapes as evidence of exploitation or resilience. Through initiatives like the Rights Lab at the University of Nottingham, my work demonstrates how Earth observation technology can illuminate hidden systems of abuse, making invisible injustices visible from space.

Doreen Boyd — Community Advisory Board

Community impact 2024–2025

At Imago, we work to empower the social research and policy community to use satellite imagery data effectively through training materials and community events, building a stronger network of users who apply these tools to real problems. Our efforts to date have focused on two main areas: developing our textbook, the *Book of Imagery*, and forming key partnerships.

The Book of Imagery

The Book of Imagery (BoI) is an open, living textbook documenting how satellite and aerial imagery can be harnessed to advance social science and policy. Developed under the Imago programme and launching at the Imago Annual Summit in December 2025, the BoI consolidates the methods, workflows and use cases that underpin Imago's imagery-based data products. **The BoI translates technical processes into accessible, reproducible guidance** for researchers, policymakers and practitioners.

The driving force behind the BoI is the persistent gap between satellite imagery's extraordinary potential and its limited adoption beyond environmental science. While imagery has long captured the physical fabric of our world, it has remained largely inaccessible to those addressing questions of prosperity, sustainability and wellbeing. **The BoI bridges this divide**, providing the knowledge infrastructure needed to make imagery useful, usable and used across disciplines.

The BoI is designed for social researchers, data practitioners and decision-makers seeking to integrate imagery into their work. It offers **conceptual grounding, technical recipes and real-world applications** in a modular, open format that encourages reuse and adaptation. Future editions will expand to include interactive notebooks and training modules. As Imago's data service evolves, the BoI will grow, serving as the enduring, public reference point for the UK's imagery-for-social-science ecosystem.

Read the BoI today at [Bol.imago.ac.uk](https://bol.imago.ac.uk)

Partnerships

Imago's partnership strategy centres on turning raw satellite imagery into information that social scientists and policymakers can use with ease. The goal is to **work with partners who help make imagery more accessible for research and policy**.

Each project aims to make imagery simple to access, understand, and apply for both new and experienced users of satellite data.

We work with three main groups of partners:

- **Data partners** supply imagery from commercial sources, open datasets, or academic projects, and their input helps improve data quality and management.
- **Distribution partners** help Imago share information by linking it to existing platforms and data systems. This allows users to find and apply imagery through tools they already use.
- **Application partners** include government agencies, research centres and social organisations. They play a vital role in using the data to study and address social and policy questions.

These partners stay involved through every stage of development, shaping each product and its results.

Interested in being a partner?
Get in touch at imago@liverpool.ac.uk

Pixel by pixel, cloud by cloud

This infographic illustrates the process we follow at Imago using one of our data products, Sun Probability Framework (SPF) — from understanding needs to delivering a technical solution with user-centred design.

Note: We generated these images using AI.
Bonus points for spotting any differences between panels!

*This approximate calculation is only for a single pass — SPF will require this many pixels to be processed several times a year.

SPF: Sun Probability Framework

Measuring sunlight exposure across the UK

Sunlight exposure shapes human behaviour, health, and wellbeing in profound ways. From mood and physical activity to the price of houses, the presence or absence of sunlight has measurable impacts on daily life. Despite its importance, researchers and policymakers have lacked accessible, high-resolution data on local sunlight conditions.

Current approaches use regional data sets that are too broad, or sun-angle calculations that can be inaccessible and computationally expensive. The Sun Probability Framework (SPF) toolkit addresses this gap by translating complex satellite cloud mask data into simple measures of sunlight probability at the geographic scales researchers already work with.

How do we do it?

SPF delivers processed sunlight exposure metrics based on cloud cover data using Sentinel-2 satellite imagery at 20-metre resolution, aggregated to Lower layer Super Output Area (LSOA) boundaries to match the geographic units used throughout UK administrative data. We calculate this using cloud mask layers, providing annual measures of sunlight availability that can be directly linked to census data, health records, survey responses, or any georeferenced dataset using standard LSOA codes.

Integration requires no GIS expertise — researchers and policymakers can merge exposure data with their existing datasets through straightforward table joins with geographic codes or administrative IDs. The toolkit includes documentation, sample integration code, and examples demonstrating the range of analyses this toolkit enables. Future releases will expand coverage to different aggregations and time periods.

Why does it matter?

Understanding how environmental conditions like sunlight affect human outcomes is essential for both understanding our societies and designing policy interventions targeting wellbeing and health inequalities.

SPF makes satellite-derived environmental data useful, usable and accessible for researchers working with UK administrative data. Whether exploring seasonal mood patterns, housing markets, or health service utilisation, researchers can now incorporate precise, localised sunlight measures into their analyses.

CLiVE: Climate Local Vulnerability and Exposure

Characterising environmental risk at local scales

Climate change is reshaping the geography and intensity of environmental hazards around the world, including the UK. Rising temperatures are contributing to more frequent and intense heatwaves, changing rainfall patterns are increasing the likelihood and severity of localised flooding, and warming-induced atmospheric changes are exacerbating episodes of air pollution.

These climate-related hazards do not affect all places or populations equally. Their impacts are shaped by the distribution of people and infrastructure, and by social and economic inequalities that influence individuals' capacity to prepare for, cope with, and recover from, adverse events.

However, our ability to systematically monitor these risks at the local scale, where impacts are experienced and decisions are made, remains limited. Many existing datasets are challenging to access due to their format or required level of technical skills. Friendly-to-access formats may fail to capture subnational variation, are not updated with sufficient frequency, or overlook key dimensions of risk such as population exposure and vulnerability.

As a result, local governments, public health agencies and researchers often lack the actionable data they need to identify priority areas, design targeted interventions and monitor progress over time.

Quantifying local vulnerability and exposure using the IPCC risk framework

CLiVE (Climate Local Vulnerability and Exposure) is a new data product designed to address this gap, providing a scientifically robust, spatially granular and policy relevant suite of indicators to quantify environmental risk across the UK. It is grounded in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) conceptualisation*, which defines risk as the interaction of three key components:

- **Hazards:** climate-related physical processes or events that may cause harm, such as extreme heat, flooding, or elevated levels of air pollution
- **Exposure:** the presence of people, assets or systems in locations that could be adversely affected by those hazards
- **Vulnerability:** the propensity or predisposition of exposed individuals or communities to be negatively impacted, influenced by factors such as age, health status, income, or housing quality

In its initial release, CLiVE focuses on developing indicators for the hazard component of risk. These indicators are derived from satellite imagery and Earth observation data, enabling consistent and scalable assessments across subnational areas of the UK. Specifically, the CLiVE toolkit includes heat stress, flood risk and air pollution.

Making satellite imagery data useful, usable and used

CLiVE is designed as an open, extensible platform delivering data in accessible and friendly-to-use formats. Future releases will incorporate indicators of population exposure, such as residential density, building typologies, or mobility patterns and social vulnerability, drawing on demographic, social, economic and infrastructure data.

The product will also expand its temporal resolution (e.g. seasonal or monthly indicators) and geographic scope (e.g. devolved administrations, national comparatives), enabling both longitudinal tracking and cross-regional comparison and analysis.

* Klein, R.J., Midgley, G.F., Preston, B.L., Alam, M., Berkhout, F.G.H., Dow, K. and Shaw, M.R., 2014. Climate change 2014: impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. IPCC fifth assessment report, Stockholm, Sweden.

RGB: Resources in Green and Built environments

Why do we need to understand green and built environments?

The presence of nature and the configuration of built environments is a critical determinant of health, wellbeing and sustainability across the UK. Exposure to conducive environments has been shown to support physical activity, reduce stress and mitigate (the effects of) air pollution and extreme heat, with broader relevance for research on car dependence, deprivation, health inequality and prosperity.

Our Resources in Green and Built environments (RGB) data product lowers the barrier for researchers and policymakers by translating complex satellite imagery into accessible, tabular indicators characterising a given environment. RGB can then be easily linked with datasets covering social, economic, and health dimensions.

What does RGB offer?

RGB provides harmonised information on the presence, quality and characteristics of different types of green and built environments across the UK.

Drawing on sources such as 10-metre-resolution Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, it provides a consistent and regularly updated national view of the location, distribution, and temporal variation of components of the built environment, supporting comparisons across both places and time.

Our initial release will be at the LSOA level, and subsequent updates will broaden the menu of geographies available to best accommodate researchers' needs.

What do we gain from understanding exposure to nature and built form?

Understanding questions such as where and whether green space is present, how compact urban development is, or to what extent both goals are compatible is essential for tackling health inequalities, designing for sustainability, and obtaining a more comprehensive picture of prosperity. RGB turns satellite data into insights that are useful, usable and widely used by researchers, urban planners and public health organisations exploring how exposure to nature and various built-up forms connects to health outcomes, social inclusion and environmental justice.

For policymakers, it highlights where investments could yield the greatest social benefits, particularly in communities facing multiple forms of deprivation. By translating satellite data into a usable, accessible format, RGB bridges the gap between environmental science, urban planning, and economics, providing a foundation for more equitable and sustainable urban and regional development.

About Smart Data Research UK

Smart Data Research UK (SDR UK) is the UK's national programme for smart data research. Delivered by the Economic and Social Research Council, it is part of the UKRI Infrastructure Fund.

Smart data is generated whenever we engage with the digital world, whether shopping online, using social media, or getting directions. When used responsibly for scientific research, this data can transform our understanding of complex social challenges.

SDR UK is delivered by a family of six data services based at leading UK universities and research organisations. Each service acquires, stewards, and enables safe access to diverse smart data within secure environments that protect privacy while enabling breakthrough research.

Healthy and Sustainable Places Data Service

Led by the University of Leeds, the Healthy and Sustainable Places Data Service addresses some of the most persistent and pressing challenges affecting health and sustainability in the UK by building access to data that has historically been beyond the reach of the research community and policymakers.

Imago Data Service for Imagery

Making satellite imagery more useful, usable, and used, Imago builds research-ready data products that can help solve the UK's most pressing challenges, from wellbeing to prosperity and sustainability. Led by researchers at the University of Liverpool, Newcastle University, the University of Manchester, and Harvard University.

Financial Data Service

A collaboration between the University of Edinburgh and Smart Data Foundry, the Financial Data Service provides unprecedented insights into the UK's economic health through secure access to de-identified banking and finance data from millions of customers.

Geographic Data Service

Led by UCL and the University of Liverpool, alongside the Oxford Saïd Business School and the University of Edinburgh, the Geographic Data Service connects different types of data through geography to study important social issues, including vulnerable populations, regional inequalities, and access to opportunities.

Smart Data Donation Service

Empowering individuals across the country to obtain their own digital footprints and share them safely with researchers. The Smart Data Donation Service is led by the University of York, with embedded partners from the Department of Culture, Media and Sport and Ofcom.

Smart Energy Data Service

Transforming our understanding of the UK's energy system through integrated data from power networks, electric vehicles, and energy meters alongside socioeconomic indicators. The Smart Energy Data Service is a consortium led by Energy Systems Catapult and the University of Oxford, in collaboration with a range of partners.

Work with us

Interested in working with Imago?

We welcome collaboration that links satellite data with social research and policy projects in areas such as sustainability, prosperity and wellbeing.

Start a conversation today by contacting the team at imago@liverpool.ac.uk

Learn more:

Website:
imago.ac.uk

Book of Imagery:
BoI.imago.ac.uk

Data catalogue:
data.imago.ac.uk

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